

MODELLING PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION DURING COOLING OF RANDOMLY-ORIENTED STRAND CARBON/PEEK COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A numerical model was developed to predict the influence of thermal gradient and moulding pressure on the pressure distribution of compression moulded randomly-oriented strand carbon/PEEK composites. The model inputs are the material's temperature dependant properties, i.e. transverse modulus and thermal shrinkage, as well as the temperature distribution of the part during cooling and the applied moulding pressure. The material properties of carbon/PEEK prepreg were measured during cooling from melt using thermal analyses. The model was employed to identify regions where pressure was lost during cooling. Validation was performed by comparing the predicted defect areas against those found on flat ROS panels moulded at 10, 30 and 50 bar.

1 INTRODUCTION

Randomly-Oriented Strand (ROS) composites consist of unidirectional pre-impregnated tape and are processed like a bulk moulding compound [1]. These materials are capable of producing highly complex parts compared to continuous fibre (CF) composites, which are generally limited to simple components having small curvature and thickness variations. From a manufacturing standpoint, ROS composites are less labour intensive than CF tapes, since cutting and preforming is not required. ROS composites also have higher fibre volume fraction than traditional short-fibre composites, thus higher mechanical properties. ROS composites are intended to be used for small intricate net-shaped compression moulded components having features such as varying wall thickness, tight radii, reinforcing ribs, mould-in holes, etc., thus being an attractive alternative for metallic components.

Studies by Feraboli *et al.* [2–5] investigated the mechanical properties of composites formed from carbon/epoxy sheet moulding compound (SMC). It was found that the material exhibits in-plane isotropic behaviour, with modulus comparable to that of CF quasi-isotropic laminates, while strength was significantly lower. The technology was employed to manufacture front and rear control arms for the Lamborghini *Sesto Elemento*, where a weight saving of 27% was obtained compared to the forged aluminum construction [5]. The excellent formability of compression moulded thermoplastic ROS composites has also been demonstrated in several other studies. Van Wijngaarden *et al.* [6] compression moulded a deep flange out of carbon/PEEK ROS composites, where it observed that the flow of the material at the processing temperature was greatly influence by the applied pressure. LeBlanc *et al.* [7] investigated the influence of the processing pressure and strand geometry on the filling of a 25 mm deep rib cavity moulded from carbon/PEEK ROS composites. A feasibility study on the manufacturing of a carbon/PEEK rotorcraft door hinge featuring net-shaped holes was presented by Eguémann *et al.* [8]. Bearing tests showed that the door hinge exhibited similar strength to that of a steel counterpart, with a weight reduction of 84%. Mechanical properties of carbon/PEEK ROS composites were also studied in detail by Selezneva *et al.* [9], where strand length and part thickness where identified as the key parameters. Finally, Picher-Martel *et al.* [10] studied the macroscopic squeeze flow by X-Ray tomography and modelled the squeeze flow in two dimensions.

Similarly to injection moulding of short-fibre reinforced thermoplastics, compression moulding of ROS composites is carried out at high pressures [7, 8]. This favours the filling of the mould cavity at

the melt temperature, and also helps compensate the thermal and crystallization shrinkage (for a semi-crystalline matrix) of the material during cooling. The latter is important in order to prevent localized loss of contact between the material and the mould, which could compromise the compaction quality of the material and lead to defect formation. This phenomenon, shown schematically in Fig. 1, can occur due to non-uniform shrinkage caused by an in-plane temperature variation [11], or in a complex feature where compaction is applied indirectly [7]. Furthermore, the high out-of-plane modulus of ROS composites owing to its high fibre volume fraction substantially reduces the ability to compensate for shrinkage, making it challenging to manufacture defect-free complex-shaped part.

A recent study by the authors in [12] showed that the loss of contact during cooling lead to porosity ranging from 0.63% to 1.3%, which affected the compression strength of the material by 15% to 25%. The defects were found to be mainly located near the surface of the panels. Moreover, higher temperature at the loss of contact resulted in higher porosity. It was also observed that no defects were formed when the pressure was lost under 300 °C at a cooling rate of 10 °C/min, suggesting that over a certain degree of crystallinity, the material has solidified enough to withstand defect formation.

This paper presents the development of a model capable of predicting the pressure distribution during cooling of compression moulded carbon/PEEK flat panels. The model inputs are the material's temperature dependant properties at a given cooling rate, i.e. thermal expansion and modulus, the temperature distribution of the part during cooling and the applied moulding pressure. The model output is the pressure distribution on the part during cooling. Critical areas where pressure is lost during and the corresponding material temperature can be identified.

Figure 1: Schematic of two circumstances where the loss of contact (shown in cross-hatched regions) between the material and the mould can occur during cooling of a compression moulded ROS composite part. (a) Non-uniform shrinkage due to an in-plane temperature variation. (b) Indirect compaction in a complex feature. Arrows on the top and bottom represent applied pressure.

2 MODELLING PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION DURING COOLING

2.1 Experimental setup

The moulding of flat ROS panels in a hot press was modelled. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2. It was inserted in an MTS (Eden Prairie, MN) 250 kN load frame. Each steel platen is 100 mm × 100 mm. A picture frame was inserted around the bottom platen to create a mould cavity. The platens were heated using a total of eight 500 W FIREROD[®] heating cartridges from Watlow (St. Louis, MO). The temperature of each platen was controlled independently by a SD Series PID controller from Watlow. The fixture was cooled using compressed air, while the cooling rate was maintained using the ramp function of the PID controllers.

Figure 2: Flat panel moulding setup. (a) Instrumented hot press. (b) Carbon/PEEK prepreg strands placed in the mould cavity before processing.

2.2 Model schematic and assumptions

All numerical simulations in this paper were performed with ANSYS[®] Mechanical Parametric Design Language. The 3-D model schematic is shown in Fig. 3. Due to symmetry in the platen temperature about the y -axis during cooling, half of the mould was modelled. The composite panel was modelled with 8-node brick element. The mould platens were modelled as rigid bodies, using rigid-deformable contact surfaces between them and the composite. This ensures that the mould platens are always parallel to each other. The list of elements used in the model is presented in Table 1.

Figure 3: Model schematic. Half of the mould/material assembly was modelled.

Table 1: Elements used in the 3-D compaction model.

Component	Elements	Degrees of freedom
Composite	SOLID226 (8 nodes)	UX, UY, UZ, TEMP
Mould platens	CONTA174 (8 nodes) TARGE170 (8 nodes)	UZ

The model's inputs and outputs are summarized in Fig. 4. Temperature dependent material properties were obtained experimentally via thermal analyses. A detailed methodology for each test is presented in Section 3.

Figure 4: Flowchart of the compaction model's inputs and outputs.

The following major assumptions were made in the present model:

- The two mould platens are perfectly parallel,
- Composite strands have no out-of-plane orientation,
- Thermal expansion of the mould platens (steel) is negligible,
- Thermal shrinkage of the composite in the fibre direction is negligible,
- The material behaviour is purely elastic (no flow).

The boundary conditions applied to the model are depicted in Fig. 5. The pressure was applied on the top platen and sliding conditions were applied to all other sides. The parallelism of the mould platens was obtained by using rigid contact elements with only one degree of freedom (z direction).

Figure 5: Boundary conditions applied to the model (2-D cross-section shown).

2.3 In-situ temperature measurements

To simplify the model and eliminate the need to perform a thermal simulation, the temperature distribution in the material during cooling was directly measured experimentally using 1 mm thick braided fibreglass thermocouples embedded at the midplane of a 24-layer CF panel with a stacking sequence of $[0/90]_{6s}$. The cooling rate of the panel was $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the temperature data was recorded at 1 Hz. A schematic of the temperature measurement locations is presented in Fig. 6a. A contour plot of the temperature distribution at a given time during cooling is presented in Fig. 6b.

3 CHARACTERIZATION OF MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The evolution of the thermomechanical properties of carbon/PEEK prepreg during cooling from melt was characterized using thermal analyses. The thermal shrinkage was measured using Thermo-mechanical Analysis (TMA), while the thermoelastic properties were characterized with Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA). Due to relatively large sample sizes and the heat transfer limitations of both instruments, the recommended heating and cooling rates are $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ or less [13], which is much lower than the cooling rates of $10\text{--}20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ typical found in compression moulding of ROS composites. Moreover, it is well known that the crystallization kinetics are influenced by cooling rates, mainly affecting the temperature range, as well as the final degree of crystallinity. Therefore, to obtain a

Figure 6: In-situ temperature measurements. (a) Thermocouple locations with respect to the mould platen. (b) Material temperature distribution during cooling. Air flows from top to bottom during cooling.

precise evolution of the thermal shrinkage and modulus at cooling rates up to 20 °C/min, a model is proposed where the properties measured at slow cooling rate are calibrated with the crystallization kinetics measured by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). The procedure is explained in the following. First, it is assumed that the crystallization ranges measured by DSC for different cooling rates are accurate, since the mass of material used for the test is very small, i.e. in the range of 5–15 mg. This is much smaller than the weight of TMA and DMA samples, typically around 0.3 g and 1.9 g, respectively. Second, for both thermal shrinkage and modulus experiments, the measured property during cooling was separated in two phases, amorphous and crystalline. Finally, the properties of the crystalline phase were adjusted to take into account the changes in the crystallization kinetics at higher cooling rates. This procedure is summarized in Fig. 7. The methodology employed for each experiment is presented in details in the following sections.

3.1 Materials

The material studied was a unidirectional carbon/PEEK slit tape, 6.35 mm wide and 0.136 mm thick, with a fibre volume fraction (V_f) of 59%. It has a glass transition temperature (T_g) of 143 °C and a melting temperature (T_m) of 343 °C. The manufacturer's recommended processing temperature is between 370 °C and 400 °C. The slit tape was cut into 25 mm long strands using a Kingsing Machinery Co. Limited (Shanghai, China) automated tape cutter, model KS-915.

3.2 Differential scanning calorimetry

All tests were performed on a TA Instruments (New Castle, DE) Q100 DSC. A stack of small prepreg flakes, approximately 2 mm × 2 mm, were inserted in each DSC pan. The samples were heated to 380 °C for 10 min to erase the crystallization history of the material [14] and then cooled to room temperature at various cooling rates: 1, 5, 10 and 20 °C/min. Each dynamic test was repeated with three different samples.

Crystallization kinetics were obtained from the DSC data by measuring the heat generated during crystallization for each dynamic test. The DSC heat flow signal was plotted as a function of time, and a linear integration of the area under the crystallization peak was used to calculate the heat generated. It was then used to obtain the weight fraction crystallinity as a function of temperature during cooling:

$$X_{mc}(T) = \frac{H_c(T)}{(1 - M_f)H_f} \quad (1)$$

where X_{mc} is the weight fraction crystallinity, H_c is the enthalpy of crystallization measured as a function of temperature, M_f is the mass fraction of fibres, and H_f is the enthalpy of fusion of the fully crystalline matrix. For PEEK resin, H_f is equal to 130.2 J/g. The mass fraction crystallinity was then converted to volume fraction crystallinity using the method presented in [15].

3.3 Thermomechanical analysis

The experiment was performed on a TA Instruments Q400 Thermomechanical Analyzer equipped with a MCA70 cooling accessory and a macro-expansion probe. A 6.3 mm square specimens were cut from a 4.3 mm thick defect-free CF carbon/PEEK panel with a stacking sequence of $[45/-45/0/90]_{4S}$. The thermal expansion of the specimen was measured during cooling from 380 °C to 25 °C in the direction perpendicular to the fibres, at a rate of 1 °C/min. More details on the thermomechanical analysis can be found in [12].

3.4 Dynamic mechanical analysis

The experiment was performed on a TA Instruments Q800 Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer equipped with a three-point bend fixture. A 55 mm × 10 mm specimen was cut from a 2.2 mm thick defect-free CF carbon/PEEK panel with a stacking sequence of $[0]_{24}$. The fibres were oriented transversely to the longitudinal direction of the specimen. To minimize specimen deformation over the melt temperature, the latter was wrapped in 0.05 mm thick kapton tape. The storage modulus was measured during cooling from 380 °C to 25 °C in the direction perpendicular to the fibres, at a rate of 1 °C/min. The test was performed at a frequency of 1 Hz and constant strain of 0.1%.

4 MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION RESULTS

4.1 Differential scanning calorimetry

The crystallization kinetics of carbon/PEEK prepreg obtained with Eq. (1) for cooling rates between 1 °C/min and 20 °C/min are presented in Fig. 8. Each curve is the average of three samples. From the results, the final X_{vc} was unaffected by the cooling rate, except at 1 °C/min where it was found to be 6% lower than the average measured value of 33.2%. As expected, the cooling rate clearly affected the temperature range of crystallization, shifting it from 297 °C – 326 °C at 1 °C/min to 250 °C – 307 °C at 20 °C/min.

Figure 8: Evolution of the volume fraction crystallinity of carbon/PEEK composite for different cooling rates.

5.3 Thermomechanical analysis

The transverse thermal and crystallization shrinkage of the carbon/PEEK sample measured at 1 °C/min is presented in Fig. 9. Since the slope of the curve is very similar before (~325 °C) and after (~295 °C) crystallization, it was separated in two components; the amorphous and crystalline phases. The thermal expansion was represented by:

$$\varepsilon_{33}(T) = (1 - V_f)(1 + \varepsilon_a + \varepsilon_c) \quad (2)$$

where ε_a is the transverse shrinkage of the amorphous phase, ε_c is the transverse shrinkage of the crystalline phase and X_{vc} is the evolution of the volume fraction crystallinity, all as a function of temperature. Assuming a linear relationship between the volume fraction crystallinity and the crystallization shrinkage, the thermal expansion of the two phases were obtained by curve fitting and are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_a(T) &= aT^3 + bT^2 + cT + d, & 200 \text{ °C} < T < 297 \text{ °C} \\ \varepsilon_a(T) &= e(T - 297) + 0.0761, & T \geq 297 \text{ °C} \\ \varepsilon_c(T) &= 0.0689X_{vc}(T) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$a = 5.32 \times 10^{-9} \frac{1}{\text{°C}^3} \quad b = -2.16 \times 10^{-6} \frac{1}{\text{°C}^2} \quad c = 5.49 \times 10^{-4} \frac{1}{\text{°C}} \quad d = -0.0354 \quad e = 6.71 \times 10^{-4} \frac{1}{\text{°C}}$$

A precise estimation of the transverse thermal strain at different cooling rates was then calculated by combining the crystallization kinetics results of Fig. 8 with Eqs. (2) and (3). The results are shown in Fig. 10.

5.3 Dynamic mechanical analysis

The transverse modulus and tan delta measured during cooling at 1 °C/min are presented in Fig. 11. The low values of tan delta observed suggest that the material behaviour is mainly elastic in the range of temperatures tested. This is likely due to the high fibre volume fraction and high viscosity of the material before crystallization. This adds confidence to the last assumption made in Section 2.2.

The transverse modulus of the composite as a function of temperature was modelled using the inverse rule of mixtures:

$$E_{33}(T) = \left(\frac{V_f}{E_f} + \frac{1 - V_f}{E_m} \right)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where E_f is the transverse modulus of the fibres, while E_m is the modulus of the matrix as a function of temperature. Since the modulus was estimated above T_g , it was assumed that only the crystallization phase contributed to the latter. Its value was obtained using curve fitting and is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} E_m(T) &= 1.76X_{vc} + aT^2 + bT + c \text{ GPa} & 200 \text{ °C} < T < 304 \text{ °C} \\ E_m(T) &= 1.76X_{vc} + d(T - 304) + 0.075 \text{ GPa} & T \geq 304 \text{ °C} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$a = -4.33 \times 10^{-5} \frac{\text{GPa}}{\text{°C}^2} \quad b = 5.92 \times 10^{-3} \frac{\text{GPa}}{\text{°C}} \quad c = 2.23 \text{ GPa} \quad d = -9.39 \times 10^{-4} \frac{\text{GPa}}{\text{°C}}$$

The value for E_f was fixed to 21 GPa [16]. It should be pointed out that the modulus of the crystalline phase used in this study doesn't reflect its real modulus of 30 GPa reported in [17]. The evolution of the transverse modulus of the composite at different cooling rates was then estimated by combining Eqs. (4) and (5) with the crystallization kinetics results of Fig. 8. The results are shown in Fig. 12.

Figure 9: Transverse thermal strain of carbon/PEEK composite separated into the amorphous and crystalline phase components. The amorphous phase component was offset for clarity.

Figure 10: Modelled transverse thermal strain of carbon/PEEK composite for different cooling rates.

Figure 11: Transverse modulus and tan delta of carbon/PEEK composite measured during cooling at 1 °C/min.

Figure 12: Modelled transverse modulus of carbon/PEEK composite for different cooling rates.

6 MODEL VALIDATION

6.1 Panel manufacturing

The numerical model was validated by comparing the predicted defect areas against the one found on flat ROS panels moulded at three different pressures. The moulding procedure was the following. Two layers of Frekote 700-NC release agent were applied on the platen surfaces and the picture frame before moulding. The prepreg strands were manually placed inside the mould cavity in small batches and shuffled in order to achieve a random in-plane distribution and minimize out-of-plane orientation. Fifty-four grams of material was used to obtain a nominal panel thickness of 3.2 mm. After the material placement, the mould was closed, a pressure of 10 bar was applied, and the press platens were heated to 380 °C. Once the target processing temperature was reached, a dwell pressure of 70 bar was applied. The material was then held at 380 °C for 15 min to ensure isothermal condition. After the dwell, the desired cooling pressure was applied and the setup was cooled to room temperature at a rate of 10 °C/min, followed by the panel ejection. The nominal moulding cycle was just above 80 min. Three cooling pressures were tested: 10, 30 and 50 bar.

6.2 Simulation

In the simulation, the composite was modelled as in-plane isotropic. The in-plane properties were assumed to have the same temperature dependence as the transverse modulus $E_{33}(T)$ defined in Eq. (4). They were calibrated with the properties measured at room temperature in [9], and are presented in Table 2. The simulation was performed as follows. For every 5 second step in the temperature measurements data (Section 2.3), the corresponding temperature was applied to each node of the finite element model. The load that corresponds to the desired moulding pressure was applied to the top platen and a solution was obtained. After each step, the position and temperature of the nodes where the pressure was zero were recorded. Once the simulation was completed, a contour plot was generated, showing the temperature at the moment when the pressure was lost on the panel.

Table 2: Temperature dependent material properties of the composite employed in the model. $E_{33}(T)$ is defined in Eq. (4).

Property	$E_x = E_y$ (GPa)	E_z (GPa)	$\nu_x = \nu_y = \nu_z$	G_{xy} (GPa)	$G_{yz} = G_{xz}$ (GPa)
Value	$3.9E_{33}(T)$	$E_{33}(T)$	0.31	$\frac{E_x}{2(1 + \nu)}$	$7.1 \frac{E_{33}(T)}{E_{33}(T)_{RT}}$

RT = Room temperature

6.3 Comparison of modelled pressure distribution with experiments

The results of the validation test for moulding pressures of 10, 30 and 50 bar are shown in Fig. 13. In the figure, the contour plots show the predicted temperature at which pressure was lost. Regions where the consolidation pressure was maintained during the entire cooling process are shown in grey. On the moulded panels, regions where pressure was lost during cooling have a white discoloration at the surface (Fig. 13b). These regions are rough to the touch and are prone to have internal porosity [12]. The outline of the defect-free region (in grey) predicted by the model were overlaid on the moulded panels.

As expected, the numerical results show that the defect area is reduced with increasing pressure. The predicted pressure loss temperatures were also reduced with increasing pressure. Their maximum values were 310.0 °C, 298.5 °C and 294.1 °C for the three moulding pressures modelled. Experimentally, this reduction translate to an increasingly smoother surface in the defect regions. Overall, a good correlation was found between the model and the experiments. Although the model doesn't agree with to the experimental threshold value of 300 °C reported in [12] under which no defects are formed, this value could be calibrated numerically by moulding defect-free panels at higher pressure.

7 CONCLUSIONS

A finite element model capable of predicting pressure distribution during cooling of ROS composites was presented. The proposed model has the capability of identifying regions where localized compaction pressure is lost during processing. Predicting such phenomenon is important as it was previously shown to cause defect formation such as voids and surface roughness. The model employs the transverse modulus and thermal shrinkage of carbon/PEEK laminates, measured as a function of temperature and cooling rate via thermal analyses. The panel temperature distribution during cooling was measured experimentally and imported in the model. The latter was solve using ANSYS® Mechanical APDL. Validation was carried out by comparing the predicted defect areas against those found on ROS flat panels moulded at three different pressures: 10, 30 and 50 bar. A good agreement was found between the experimental and numerically predicted defects regions.

The results from this study constitute an initial step in the development of a model capable of predicting defect formation in complex-shaped ROS parts. Used in conjunction with a thermal simulation of the process, it is intended to be employed to identified problematic areas on a part during the tooling design step. The part and tooling geometries, as well as the cooling strategy could then be optimized in order to reduce the risk of defect formation. Such tool would thus greatly reduce the trial and error often required to successfully manufacture defect-free ROS composite parts.

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Figure 13: Comparison between the model and the experiments. (a) Model showing the temperature at which pressure was lost during cooling. (b) Experimental panels showing surface defects and the outline of the defect-free region predicted by the model. Air flows from top to bottom during cooling.

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